

$C_{12}H_{12}N_2O$ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.0%) IR: $\nu_{\max}^{KBr}$ cm^{-1} : 1575 (C=C), 1613 (C=N), 3333 (O-H stretching), 1190 (O-H bending), 2778 (C-H stretching), 1390 (C-O stretching).

4,6-Dimethyl-5-(arylo)pyrimidin-2-ol: To a well cooled and stirred solution of 4,6-dimethyl pyrimidin-2-ol (0.31 g; 0.0025 mol) in ethanol containing sodium hydroxide (10 ml; 1 N) was gradually added a diazotised solution of base (0.0025 mol). 4,6-Dimethyl-5-(arylo)pyrimidin-2-ol, which separated out on acidification and dilution with water, was crystallised either from ethanol or DMF-ethanol or GAA-ethanol mixture as a coloured solid.

Similar set of reaction was carried out with 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)pyrimidin-2-ol to get 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)-5-(arylo)pyrimidin-2-ol and all the compounds of the two series are recorded in Tables 1 and 3.

TABLE 1—4,6-DIMETHYL-5-(ARYLO)PYRIMIDIN-2-OLS
(Ia: $R_1=R_2=CH_3$; Ar= C_6H_4R)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent
1.	H	219	BL	46	DMF/EtOH
2.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	158	B	39	DMF/EtOH
3.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	165	B	38	DMF/EtOH
4.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	245	BL	41	GAA/EtOH
5.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	228	B	52	DMF/EtOH
6.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	225	B	56	DMF/EtOH
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	240	B	58	DMF/EtOH
8.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	247	B	52	DMF/EtOH
9.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	241	B	54	Py/EtOH
10.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	212	B	53	DMF/EtOH
11.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	191	B	57	EtOH
12.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	300	BL	40	DMF/EtOH
13.	<i>m</i> -Methoxy	158	B	39	EtOH
14.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	118	B	40	GAA/EtOH
15.	2,5-Dichloro	262	BL	60	DMF/EtOH

TABLE 2—4,6-DIMETHYL-5-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO)PYRIMIDIN-2-OLS
(IIa: $R_1=R_2=CH_3$; Ar= $C_6H_4SO_2NHR$)

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent
1.	Acetyl	252	B	43	DMF/EtOH
2.	Phenyl	250	B	38	DMF/EtOH
3.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	238	B	40	DMF/EtOH
4.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	227	BL	42	DMF/EtOH
5.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	107	B	43	Cyclohexane/ Benzene
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	245	BL	45	DMF/EtOH
7.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	236	BL	40	DMF/EtOH
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	243	B	45	DMF/EtOH
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	255	B	53	DMF/EtOH
10.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	240	B	50	DMF/EtOH
11.	4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidin-2-yl	267	BL	44	DMF/EtOH

4,6-Dimethyl- and 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)-5-(N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)-pyrimidin-2-ols were similarly synthesised and are recorded in Tables 2 and 4.

TABLE 3—4-METHYL-6-(*p*-METHYLPHENYL)-5-(ARYLO)PYRIMIDIN-2-OLS

[Ib: $R_1=CH_3$; $R_2=C_6H_4CH_3(p)$; Ar= C_6H_4R]

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent
1.	H	147	RB	38	EtOH
2.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	129	B	31	EtOH
3.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	232	B	31	EtOH
4.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	223	B	34	GAA/EtOH
5.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	277	R	44	DMF/EtOH
6.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	135	B	45	DMF/EtOH
7.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	266	R	52	DMF/EtOH
8.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	298	B	48	DMF/EtOH
9.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	278	R	46	DMF/EtOH
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	297	B	50	DMF/EtOH
11.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	217	B	40	DMF/EtOH
12.	<i>m</i> -Methoxy	156	B	39	DMF/EtOH
13.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	264	B	41	DMF/EtOH
14.	2,5-Dichloro	127	Y	47	EtOH

TABLE 4—4-METHYL-6-(*p*-METHYLPHENYL)-5-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL BENZENEAZO)PYRIMIDIN-2-OLS

[Iib: $R_1=CH_3$; $R_2=C_6H_4CH_3(p)$; Ar= $C_6H_4SO_2NHR$]

Sl. No.	R	m.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Crystallisation solvent
1.	H	227	B	52	DMF/EtOH
2.	Acetyl	274	B	38	DMF/EtOH
3.	Phenyl	122	B	38	EtOH
4.	<i>o</i> -Methylphenyl	204	R	42	DMF/EtOH
5.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	205	R	40	DMF/EtOH
6.	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	225	B	42	Py/EtOH
7.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	269	R	42	DMF/EtOH
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	275	R	40	EtOH
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	172	O	43	GAA/EtOH
10.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	178	R	42	DMF/EtOH
11.	Guanidyl	281	RB	44	DMF/EtOH
12.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	226	B	46	DMF/EtOH
13.	4,6-Dimethyl pyrimidin-2-yl	253	B	42	DMF/EtOH
14.	2,6-Dimethyl pyrimidin-4-yl	277	RB	44	GAA/EtOH
15.	4,6-Dimethoxy pyrimidin-2-yl	161	B	45	GAA/EtOH

GAA = Glacial acetic acid; DMF = Dimethyl formamide; Py = Pyridine; B = Brown; O = Orange; R = Red; BL = Black.

All the compounds gave consistent elemental analysis.

During the course of coupling reactions, it was observed that the presence of non-polar groups like alkyl or aryl at positions 4 and 6 retarded the rate of coupling, thereby giving lower yields which was in accordance with the work reported earlier⁹ that only polar groups enhanced the rate of coupling reactions. It was also observed that replacement of methyl by *p*-toluyl at position 6 further reduced the rate of coupling, resulting in lower yields and it could be attributed to the steric effect of this bulky group.

The ir spectral studies of 4,6-dimethyl- and 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)-5-(arylo/N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrimidin-2-ols revealed the presence of N=N group by absorbing in the region 1535-1567 cm^{-1} . The respective asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrational modes of

S=O, from sulphonamide group appeared at $\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In the nmr spectral studies of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-ol in DMSO(D_6), the singlets at 2.28, 6.48 and 9.26 δ appeared due to CH_3 , pyrimidine ring C-H and O-H protons respectively. However, in case of 4-methyl-6-(*p*-methylphenyl)-pyrimidin-2-ol, two methyl groups attached to pyrimidine ring and benzene ring were characterised by two singlets at 2.15 δ and 2.25 δ respectively; the proton of the pyrimidine ring in this compound was observed at 6.72 δ . The aromatic protons were represented by two doublets centered at 7.2 δ (2H, *ortho* to methyl group) and 7.85 δ (2H, *ortho* to thiazole ring) while the O-H protons by a singlet at 9.2 δ . The absence of singlet at 6.48 δ and 6.72 δ in the coupled products of the two series of compounds confirmed that coupling had taken place.

Antibacterial properties: When screened at 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 4,6-dimethyl-5-(aryloxy)pyrimidin-2-ols exhibited activity of varying degree against all the three micro-organisms and the order of activity was $P. pyocyanea > S. aureus > E. coli$. On comparing the activities of the different compounds, it was observed that the introduction of methyl group in the arylazo group decreased the activity. However, the replacement of this methyl by an electron withdrawing group like halogen atom or a nitro group caused an enhancement in the activity, particularly against *P. pyocyanea*. Further, the exchange of methyl at position 6 by a tolyl group decreased the activity against *P. pyocyanea* while the activity against *E. coli* increased to a considerable extent, there being no marked effect on *S. aureus*.

Another important observation made in the course of this work was that replacement of the arylazo group by sulphonamido group rendered these compounds less active.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-Phenyl-3-methyl/phenyl-4-(*o/m/p*-substituted benzeneazo)-5-pyrazolones, 1-Phenyl-3-(*o/m/p*-substituted anilic)-5-pyrazolones and 3-Methyl/phenyl-4-(*o/m/p*-substituted benzeneazo)-5-isoxazolones as Possible Biological Agents

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EXTENSIVE work on the applications of 5-pyrazolones, isoxazolones and their derivatives in chemotherapy has been reported¹⁻⁵. Pyrazolones have also been used in analytical chemistry⁶. Keeping this in view some substituted benzene diazonium chlorides were coupled with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl benzoylacetate and subsequent refluxing of the resulting products (I) with phenylhydrazine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively gave the pyrazolones (II) and isoxazolones (III). The reaction, in general, may be represented as follows:

Some anilic-5-pyrazolones were also synthesised by condensing malonanilic acids with phenylhydrazine. Purity and homogeneity of all the compounds were checked by tlc and elemental analysis.

Experimental

Melting points recorded are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken in KBr film on a Beckmann IR spectrophotometer. Malonanilic acids required for the work were synthesised by the method of Singhal and Ittyerah⁷.

Ethyl-4-bromo-2-methyl benzeneazo acetoacetate (I): 4-Bromo-2-methyl aniline (1.86 g) was diazotised in the usual manner. The filtered diazonium solution was run slowly into a well cooled mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (1.95 g) in ethanol (2.5 ml) and sodium acetate (10 g) in water (2.5 ml). A